

H2020 - 700478

RAmars for loNG distance maritime surveillancE and Search and Rescue opeRations

D8.4 RANGER INFORMATION KIT

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Executive summary

The current deliverable constitutes a report about the dissemination materials that were created and deployed to support the communication, dissemination and awareness raising activities of the project within **Task 8.1 Awareness Raising Strategies**. The information kit includes the project leaflet, poster, roll up banner, videos, the project's newsletter issues and any other relevant communication and dissemination material (*digital and printable*) used for presenting the RANGER in a variety of events for promoting it to potential users. **D8.4 Information Kit** is based on, and is consistent with, the DoA and the CA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the dissemination material (*printable and digital*) created for communicating and promoting the project and its results in various events (*workshops, conferences, exhibitions, meetings etc.*)

1.2 Intended Audience

Intended Audience	Reason to read
RANGER partners	to be informed about the dissemination materials created and used during the project’s lifecycle.
European Commission	this is a deliverable of the RANGER project and reports about the dissemination materials deployed for assisting in the promotion of the project and its results.
Target Groups <i>(national authorities, coast guards, Navies, FRONTEX and EUROSUR, CISE etc.)</i>	to get informed as well as to raise awareness about the topic of the project.
Representatives of similar EU funded projects	to be informed about best practices in terms of communicating projects under similar topic.
Anyone interested	to be informed about the topic of the project, raise awareness and learn about best practices for promoting a project and its results in a pan-European level.

Table 1: Intended Audience

1.3 Structure of the Document

This deliverable is consisted of 5 chapters and two annexes. The **first chapter** is an introductory one where the reader is informed about the purpose of the document, the audience that is addressed to and its structure. The **second chapter** presents the printable materials that the RANGER communication team created throughout the project’s lifecycle. The **third** showcases the RANGER giveaways/mementos distributed at important events and the **fourth chapter** the digital dissemination materials. The **fifth** chapter concludes this deliverable. Lastly, **Annex A** constitutes the list of acronyms where the reader can find the explanation of each abbreviation mentioned within this document; and **Annex B** ethical issues related to the D8.4.

2 Printable Dissemination Material

Printed dissemination materials were produced throughout the duration of the RANGER project for raising awareness. They were used for presenting the project in various events such as workshops, conferences, exhibitions and so on for promoting it to potential users and overall to stakeholders. These materials (*together with the newsletter issues*) compose the core “*information kit*” of the project which has been created since the beginning of RANGER and includes two versions of a **poster**, a **leaflet** and a **roll up banner**.

In addition to the above materials, the **newsletter issues** that have been published during the course of the project they have been printed upon communication and dissemination needs of the project. However, in this deliverable RANGER newsletter issues are considered digital dissemination materials (*section 4.1 Newsletter*) due to the fact that they were mainly communicated and distributed via online channels such as RANGER website, emails to newsletter subscribers, partners’ networks and so on.

All promotional materials in printable format are available at the RANGER website, on section “*Information Centre*”, subsection “*Dissemination Kit*” so anyone interested can find them online. For reader’s ease we have accumulated all the available ones at the table below while further information about them is given in sections that follow.

Material	Version	Available at RANGER website (URL)
Leaflet	1 st version	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Leaflet-Ranger_16X22_prefinal_consortium.pdf
	2 nd version	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/ranger_leaflet_11-2018_v12_lowres.pdf
Poster	1 st version	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Poster_Ranger_v17b_v10.pdf
	2 nd version	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Poster_Ranger_update_2019_v13-Final.pdf
Roll up Banner	1 st version	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/RANGER-banner.pdf
	2 nd version	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Banner_Ranger_v2.pdf

Table 2: List of RANGER printable materials available online

2.1 Leaflet

The project’s leaflet is tri-fold, sized **16x22 cm** when folded (*48x22 cm when opened*). During the course of RANGER two versions were created, same size and layout, and included information as follows:

- **1st version:** project’s logo and its full acronym, project aim description, objectives, expected impact, validation pilots, the main features of RANGER, partners’ logos (*consortium presentation*), contact information, project’s website (*URL*), QR code linked with the website, project’s social media accounts, the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text. A representation of this version’s layout, outside and inside, is provided in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2** respectively.
- **2nd version:** project’s logo and its full acronym, project aim, expected impact, description of the Advanced User Interface, validation of pilots, partners’ logos (*consortium presentation*), contact information, the RANGER social media accounts, project's website (*URL*), the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text. A representation of this version’s layout, outside and inside, is provided in **Figure 3** and **Figure 4** respectively.

CONSORTIUM

- EXUS Software LTD (EXUS)
- Diginext Sarl (DXT)
- Institute Of Communication and Computer Systems ICCS
- Technische Universität Dresden (TUD)
- LAUREA- Ammattikorkeakoulu OY (LAU)
- LEONARDO S.p.A. (LDO)
- Teletso Technologies Pireforiniks kai Epikoinonion EPE (TEL)
- NATO Science and Technology Organisation (NATO)
- Ministry of National Defence (HMDD)
- Ministère de la Transition écologique et solidaire (DMA)

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www.ranger-project.eu

RAdars for lo**NG** distance maritime surveillance**E** and Sa**R** operations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 700708

Figure 1: Leaflet 1st version - Outside layout

Project Aim

RANGER is an EU funded project, within the H2020 Horizon programme. RANGER innovates by combining novel and ground-breaking Radar technologies with innovative supporting technological solutions for early warning, in view of delivering a surveillance platform that will offer tracking as well as detection, recognition, and identification of vessels far beyond existing legacy radar systems.

The main goal of RANGER is to provide innovative solutions for early warning and distant border surveillance to support search-and-rescue operations and tackle illegal conduct in the marine environment. For RANGER to deliver its value to the targeted audience (end-users and society), the envisaged solution will drastically improve the performance of existing Radar systems, by employing a blend of Over the Horizon Radar system and Photonics Enhanced MIMO radar system with other novel supporting technologies for data fusion and early warning and existing infrastructures, validated in the context of real pilot exercises.

Project Objectives

1. To provide a complete solution for maritime surveillance and Search and Rescue operations.
2. To lower the total cost of ownership compared to existing marine surveillance platforms and radar solutions.
3. To ensure compatibility of the RANGER platform with the Common Information Sharing Environment – CISE.
4. To validate and demonstrate the effectiveness of the integrated RANGER platform.
5. To define a multilevel compliance framework (ethical - legal - societal) that RANGER solution will be aligned with.

RANGER Platform

Validation Pilots

- Pilot 1**
The first pilot will be implemented in France with the collaboration of technical partners and French end-user partners (DMA).
- Pilot 2**
The second pilot will be implemented in a completely different maritime environment, in Greece (Igeion Sea). It will be conducted by HMDD with the support of the technical RANGER partners.

Expected impact

Research & Innovation

- OTH (Over-The-Horizon) Radar
- Photonics Enhanced MIMO (PE-MIMO) Radar
- Data Fusion and Machine Learning
- Early Warning Engine (EWE)

Maritime Surveillance & Operations

- Improvement of Search and Rescue Operations
- Early detection of small vessels
- Optimization of end-user resources
- Efficient coordination of SAR operations
- Automated and self-learning platform
- Early warnings and detection alerts
- Timely response & appropriate measures
- Reinforcement of European and National Coordination Centres position
- Generation of a common situational picture
- Improved detection and on-time identification of non-collaborative small vessels

Socio-economic benefits

- Citizens
- Improved maritime security
- Enhanced SAR capability
- Protection of human rights
- Opportunities stemming from technological breakthroughs
- Maritime surveillance market
- Delivery of an economic and operationally viable solution
- Environment
- Friendly and unobtrusive solution to the deployment environment

Figure 2: Leaflet 1st version - Inside layout

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- LEONARDO S.p.A. (LDO)
- Teletso Technologies Pireforiniks kai Epikoinonion EPE (TEL)
- NATO Science and Technology Organisation (NATO)
- Ministry of National Defence (HMDD)
- Ministère de la Transition écologique et solidaire (DMA)

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www.ranger-project.eu

RAdars for lo**NG** distance maritime surveillance**E** and Sa**R** operations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 700708

Figure 3: Leaflet 2nd version - Outside layout

Figure 4: Leaflet 2nd version - Inside layout

2.2 Poster

The RANGER poster, suitable for placing it on wall or pin board, is sized **70x100 cm** and includes both textual and graphic elements of the project. During the RANGER lifecycle two versions were created, same size and layout, and included information as follows:

- **1st version:** project's full acronym and its logo, facts and figures, contact details of the project coordinator, presentation of Main features, partners' logos (*consortium presentation*), RANGER website (*URL*), QR code linked with the project's website, the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text. A representation of this version's layout is provided in **Figure 5**.
- **2nd version:** RANGER logo, the project's motto "*Extending the boundaries of safety in maritime environment*", fact and figures, contact details of the project coordinator, graphic representation of the RANGER system, Key Features, partners' logo (*consortium presentation*), RANGER website (*URL*), QR code linked with the project's website, the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text. A representation of this version's layout is provided in **Figure 6**.

Figure 5: RANGER Poster 1st version

Figure 6: RANGER Poster 2nd version

2.3 Roll Up Banner

The RANGER roll up banner is made of aluminum and it is light weighted and portable. It is consisted of four parts: **a)** the aluminum base, **b)** the banner, **c)** the banner’s stand (*aluminum pole*), and **d)** the slotted top rail. Sized **80X200 cm** it was created in order to provide a brief overview of the project and for improving the project’s visibility at conferences, exhibitions, workshops, meetings and other dissemination events. During the course of the project two versions were created, same size and layout, and included information as follows:

- **1st version:** project's full acronym and its logo, facts and figures, contact details of the project coordinator, presentation of Main features, partners logos (*consortium presentation*), RANGER website (*URL*), QR code linked with the project's website, the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text. A representation of this version’s layout is provided in **Figure 7**.
- **2nd version:** RANGER logo, the project's moto "*Extending the boundaries of safety in maritime environment*", fact and figures, contact details of the project coordinator, graphic representation of the RANGER system, Key Features, partners' logo (*consortium presentation*), RANGER website (*URL*), QR code linked with the project's website, the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text. A representation of this version’s layout is provided in **Figure 8**.

Figure 7: Roll Up Banner 1st version

Figure 8: Roll Up Banner 2nd version

2.4 Final Workshop Agenda

The consortium organized on the 20th of November 2019 its Final Workshop in the city of Chania, in Crete island (*Greece*). An Agenda was created and printed as supplementary material in order to support the communication actions in inviting the participants (*experts, representatives from similar EU funded project, public maritime authorities etc.*) at the event.

This 3-page material, A4 paper sized, included an **introductory paragraph** about the RANGER project and a **summary of the workshop**. Moreover, contact details of the organizing team were also provided for getting in touch with them (*if needed*).

The main part, though, of this material included the **Agenda** of the workshop (*topics, duration, speakers, organizations*). Also, it had printed on the EU emblem and required acknowledgment text, partners' logo (*consortium presentation*), the RANGER website (*URL*), contact details with the project coordinator and project's social media accounts. A visual representation of the Final Workshop Agenda is shown in **Figure 9**, with information included only in its last page in order to avoid disclosing potential sensitive information.

1:00	13:25	14:25	Open Discussion: Future use of RANGER solution - Collaboration with other EU Funded projects	ALL
1:00	14:25	15:25	Lunch + Group Photo	
0:30	15:25	15:55	Banner Session	ALL
0:15	15:55	16:10	Closure by RANGER Coordinator	EXUS

Contact us:

RANGER project's Coordinator: Dimitris Katsaros, d.katsaros@exus.co.uk

RANGER project Website: www.ranger-project.eu

Find us on Twitter & LinkedIn

 <https://twitter.com/H2020Ranger>

 <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12014068/>

RANGER Consortium

 This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement no 700478.

Figure 9: Final Workshop Agenda (last page)

3 Giveaways/Mementos

In the framework of performing activities that would assist the dissemination efforts of the consortium and further increase its visibility, we designed, printed and distributed **giveaways/mementos** which included the RANGER branding (*including website URL*), the EU emblem and the grant number. The most of them were created in October 2019 and handed out at events of utmost importance that RANGER organized during the final phase of the project. The first batch of mementos were given at the [MSE2019](#) event (29th – 31st October 2019) that was co-organized by the RANGER consortium. The second batch was given to the participants of the **Final RANGER Workshop** held in Crete, Greece on the 20th November 2019.

Figure 10: Giveaways/mementos

Figure 11: Giveaways/mementos distributed at MSE2019 event (RANGER booth)

3.1 Organic Cotton Bag

This eco-friendly bag had printed on it the **project’s logo**, the RANGER **website (URL)**, the **EU emblem** and the **acknowledgement text** “*This project has received funding from the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement no 700478*”.

Figure 12: Fabric Bags

3.2 Pen

The pen had printed on it the **project's logo**, the URL of RANGER's **website**, the **EU emblem** and the **grant agreement number**.

Figure 13: Pens

3.3 Notepad

The notepad included the **RANGER logo**, the project's **full acronym** "*RAdars for loNG distance maritime surveillancE and SaR operations*", the URL of RANGER's **website**, the **EU emblem** and the **acknowledgement text** "*This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement no 700478*".

Figure 14: Notepads

3.4 Envelop

The envelop was printed in order to enclose materials such as the notepad, the pen, the Agenda (*Final Workshop case*), the leaflet and being distributed as promotional package (*together with the fabric bag*) during the events that RANGER organized. Its layout included the project's full acronym and its logo, contact details of the project coordinator, the partners' logo (*consortium presentation*), the RANGER website (*URL*), QR code linked with the project's website, the EU emblem and the acknowledgement text to the EU.

Figure 15: Envelops

3.5 Lanyards & Badges

Within the context of supporting the communication activities made for the **Final Workshop** we designed and printed badges that included the **name** of each participant of the workshop, the **name of the organization** that they represented, the **RANGER logo** and the **QR code** linked to RANGER website. The lanyards had printed on the project's logo.

Figure 16: Lanyards & Badges

4 Digital Dissemination Material

4.1 Newsletter

As already been mentioned in other related deliverables of WP8 (*i.e. D8.5, D8.6 and D8.7*), the RANGER newsletter delivered information on project findings and developments and it was disseminated to stakeholders through various channels. While the specific tool primarily targeted the European research community, national authorities and the rest target groups of RANGER it was also addressed to the general public, for awareness raising purposes.

The newsletter was disseminated via the project’s website, emails to subscribers, partners’ networks and RANGER social media accounts. **Eleven issues** have been published till the submission time of the current deliverable and are available on the [project’s website](#). The following table presents all issues published so far accompanied with a short description per each.

Period	Issue No.	Description	URL
May 2016 to April 2017 (Y1)	No.1 (Sept. 2016)	This first newsletter is an introduction to the RANGER project and its main objectives	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/RANGER-Newsletter-1.pdf
	No.2 (Nov. 2016)	The ethical and societal dimensions of the RANGER solution were discussed, and the project-related updates were presented.	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/RANGER-Newsletter-2.pdf
	No.3 (Feb. 2017)	Informs the readers about the Site Survey in Crete, in preparation of the RANGER validation pilots, and about our participation and project presentation at the European Coast Guard Functions Forum	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/RANGER-Newsletter-3.pdf
May 2017 to April 2018 (Y2)	No.4 (May 2017)	Features an interview from the Technical Manager of the RANGER project, who provides an overview of the expected RANGER benefits and technology advances while highlighting the core components of the RANGER system; and a study on Radar Cross Section, realized by Diginext	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/4th_newsletter_v7.pdf
	No.5 (Oct. 2017)	Features an article on the RANGER solutions and societal responsibility, by LAUREA; and project updates	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/RANGER-Newsletter-3.pdf
	No.6 (Apr. 2018)	Features two articles about the expected impact of the RANGER technology on Surveillance and on Search and Rescue operations. It also includes project news and updates	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/6th_newsletter_v3.pdf
May 2018 to April 2019 (Y3)	No. 7 (Sep. 2018)	Features an article about the RANGER project’s integration testing activities. It also includes project news and updates as well as related conferences & events.	https://www.ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/7th_newsletter_8.pdf
	No.8 (Jan. 2019)	Features an article about the RANGER project’s 1st Pilot demonstration and another one about RANGER Rx receiver installation. It also includes project news and updates as well as related conferences & events.	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/8th_newsletter_lowres_v7.pdf

May 2019 to December 2019 (Y4)	No. 9 <i>(May 2019)</i>	Features an article about Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) and an article about the 1st Maritime Situational Awareness Workshop (MSAW) 2019. It also includes project news and updates as well as related conferences & events	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/9th-newsletter_lowres_v4-1.pdf
	No. 10 <i>(Aug. 2019)</i>	Features an article entitled Smart Borders, Surveillance and Data Protection by Dr. Lilian Mitrou (University of the Aegean), an article about the installation of the MIMO radar by Niko Joram (TUD) and another article about the 2nd RANGER Pilot Demonstration, by the RANGER coordinator Dimitris Katsaros (EXUS). It also includes project news and updates as well as related conferences & events.	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/10th-newsletter.pdf
	No.11 <i>(Dec. 2019)</i>	Features five articles that present the RANGER activities and are about the first Greek Demonstration Pilot, the Mediterranean Security Event 2019 (MSE2019), the 1st Maritime Situational Awareness Workshop (MSAW), the final Greek Demonstration Pilot and the final RANGER Workshop. Lastly, it includes an announcement of the official release of the promotional video that our consortium created from the 2nd French Pilot Demonstration.	Link not available at the time of submission.

Table 3: RANGER Newsletter Issues

4.2 Press Release

The first press release was created in October 2018 in English and circulated to the consortium in order to promote it at their own channels and networks. It was announcing the realization of the RANGER first Pilot in real environment and validated successfully its integrated platform. Moreover, during the same period, a press release in French was published and it was based on the English version that was circulated. Both versions are available online at project’s website on “*Information Centre*” section, “*Press releases/Press clippings*” subsection. A final press release is planned to be published by the completion of the RANGER lifecycle to announce the end of the project.

No.	Press release	URL
1.	The RANGER EU project realised its first Pilot in real environment and validated successfully its integrated platform. (Press release in English)	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/RANGER-press-release-1st-Pilot-2.pdf
2.	Press release in French	https://ranger-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Ranger-french-press-release.pdf
3.	Announcing the end of the RANGER lifecycle	Link not available at submission time of this deliverable.

Table 4: RANGER Press Releases

Figure 17: Press release in English (3-page)

Figure 18: Press release in French (2-page)

4.3 Videos

The RANGER consortium created four videos in order to advertise the achievements and progress of the project. The **first video** was created on the occasion of the implementation of the 1st French RANGER Pilot Demonstration that was held in October 2018. The **second video** made by TUD with ships that were detected with the PE MIMO radar which was installed at Cap Bear during the 2nd French RANGER Pilot Demonstration. The **third video** was prepared in October 2019 and it was about the implementation of the 2nd French RANGER Pilot Demonstration. It presents interviews by the RANGER Coordinator and several project partners as well as shots taken during the demonstration from the vessels that participated. The **fourth video** showcased the second Greek pilot as well as the Final RANGER workshop. All videos are available online at the [RANGER YouTube channel](#). The following table lists the project's videos along with their links at YouTube.

No.	Video	Title	URL
1.	<p>and the PE-MIMO radars were successfully tested.</p>	RANGER 1st Pilot Demonstration	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xoNj6SZzLTM
2.	<p>Container ship passing at 2800m</p>	Technische Universitat Dresden (TUD) mimo radar demo	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=auWy0pRrrsU
3.	Marco EVANGELISTA Project Engineering Manager at Leonardo </p>	RANGER H2020 project - 2nd French Pilot	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RhX7uvyKYFk
4.		RANGER H2020 project - 2nd Greek Pilot	Link not available at submission time

Table 5: RANGER Videos

5 Conclusions

During the 44 months of the project's lifecycle the consortium deployed various methods to disseminate the project's results, raise its visibility and awareness around RANGER. Within this framework in order to support such actions several printable and digital materials were created, communicated and distributed (*printable materials case*) in third party events such as exhibitions, workshops, conferences etc. and in events that RANGER project team organized. The current deliverable presented in detail these materials and the information that contained per each.

Annex A - List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
cm	centimetre
D8.5	D8.5 Inventory of communication, dissemination and raising awareness activities (first year)
D8.6	D8.6 Inventory of communication, dissemination and raising awareness activities (second year)
D8.7	D8.7 Inventory of communication, dissemination and raising awareness activities (third year)
EU	European Union
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
HMOD	Ministry of National Defence
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
MSAW2019	Maritime Situational Awareness Workshop
MSE2019	Mediterranean Security Event 2019
NATO STO-CMRE	Science and Technology Organization Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation
PU	Public
QR code	Quick Response code
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP8	Work Package 8

Annex B – Ethical Issues (related to the D8.4)

Deliverable		D8.4 RANGER Information Kit	
Activity		Main Responsibility	How are the guidelines applied?
1	<p>Development of RANGER Code of Conduct and follow-up of the current discussion on maritime surveillance</p> <p>The initial RANGER Code of Conduct provided in the Deliverable 3.1 is to be developed and specified more in detail during the RANGER project. Separate versions of the Code of Conduct are needed for RANGER as stand-alone version and for RANGER as part of EUROSUR/CISE.</p>	Project management and ethics committee working.	N/A for D8.4
2	<p>Legal framework follow-up regarding maritime surveillance and its technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Especially since RANGER may change the moral division of labor in maritime surveillance (e.g. in SAR where much more information will be available), it may even be a mean to change to the legislation (or how it will be interpreted) Follow both EU and local legislation and standards (radiation, environment, NATURA2000 etc.) from the design phase of the radars. Be especially aware of the changing legislation. 	Each WP	N/A for D8.4
3	<p>Proper understanding of maritime surveillance operations & involvement of end-users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> End-users are to be involved in the project during its <u>whole life span</u>. End-users should come from various levels of maritime surveillance and from various operations in EU and member states (search and rescue, border control, fisheries control, customs, environment). Representatives from the third countries from Mediterranean coast site also to be involved in project, as well as various non-government organizations. <p>In addition make it sure that in the research work with the end-users consent forms are always collected and the collection & processing of personal data is avoided.</p>	All the work-packages working with end-users.	N/A for D8.4
4	<p>EUROSUR/CISE collaboration in ethics work</p> <p>Since EUROSUR and CISE probably has already taken into account the critics of forgetting humanities in favour of security and new businesses, it is crucial that RANGER’s interoperability and compliance with EUROSUR and CISE covers also these ethical issues (not only technology). This includes especially the following issues:</p>	Project management team (with the help of ethics committee)	N/A for D8.4

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-refoulement and the use of RANGER radar to detect vessels on high sea and on the water territories of third countries. • Seeking for the solution how we will deliver the long-distance information RANGER provides also to neighbouring third countries so that they can also enhance their SAR activities. • Seeking for the fair moral division of labour in providing assistance in a situation in which we constantly get distress information outside country's own SAR –regions. 		
5	<p>RANGER business/governance modelling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RANGER as stand-alone solution, and especially its user processes and business/business model need to be designed carefully, including the user training and selling/procurement strategy which avoids the biased use of RANGER in border control and SAR. - Productizing a feasibility study and societal impact assessment about RANGER and its use in the proposed area before the implementation as part of the “RANGER package”, including needed activities to eliminate undesirable consequences beforehand. - When selling RANGER as stand-alone solution, follow up of the consequences of the use of RANGER technology is needed to provide as part of the “RANGER service package”. - Selling RANGER only for the use of municipalities or other authorized bodies (>the avoidance of the misuse and dual-use) - Licensing 	WP 8	N/A for D8.4
6	<p>Design of the RANGER technology/Data management and security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Privacy by design” and other requirements (anonymizing etc.) defined in the coming new Data Protection legislation (Act + Directive). - Specific Data security standards are to be followed - User logs as part of the system. - Check and balance approach - Limit the access to the RANGER data only to relevant authorities (access rights, ranger business modelling) - Rules & regulation on the use of data 	Technical partners	N/A for D8.4
7	<p>Design of the RANGER technology/ The modifications of the user interface according the users background/maritime surveillance aspect</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SAR criterion, human rights and other ethical guidelines should be taken into account when developing the RADAR 	Ethics committee and technical partners	N/A for D8.4

	<p>technology, its processes and business model.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The language and terminology of the user interface should serve each aspect of maritime surveillance (by taking into account the status of the user logged in) 		
8	<p>Design of the RANGER technology/Physical design of the radar antennas</p> <p>Hire industrial designer etc. to create beautiful antennas and radars.</p>	WP4	N/A for D8.4
9	<p>Continuous societal impact assessment of RANGER during the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint societal impact assessment with all the work packages will be done in the mid and end of the project under the work of ethics committee and documented in D3.2. This concern especially the Mediterranean area where the system is to be piloted. Also expertise from other areas than maritime surveillance are needed in order to figure out the impacts on society (e.g. irregular immigration) • In addition each wp is expected to conduct SIA among their own stakeholders 	Ethics committee and each work-package	N/A for D8.4
10	<p>Communication and dissemination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good PR and information with local communities. <p>Make communities understand both the benefits and disadvantages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is necessary in the RANGER dissemination and communication use the terms “irregular” “asylum” and “illegal” in a logical and informative way. 	WP8	All the communication and dissemination activities that have taken place are according to the ethical guidelines related to Communication and Dissemination as described here.
11	<p>Guidelines for the installation and use of the system</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rules & regulation on the use of data. Training as part of the RADAR implementation on necessary also from this point of view. - Consider environmental studies when installing the antenna, and be in contact with archaeological experts before installing the system. Have agreements from local/national authorities to install and use HF waves - The installation of the radars in a places which are already occupied for same kind of activities (e.g. military bases) - Choose the right location for the radar that doesn't cause problems to the nature, archaeological sites, tourism. To mitigate 	WP7 + trials	N/A for D8.4

	<p>human exposure in radiation, the OTH radars can be located in unpopulated areas. Further minimize the power levels by improving the directivity of the radar.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety instructions are also needed for installing radars and doing maintenance work. 		
12	<p>Follow-up of the implementation of these guidelines</p> <p>Work Packages (WPs) and their deliverables (in which an ethical and societal compliance check is to be added as an annex of each deliverable).</p>	Each WP	